

BIG FIVE PERSONALITY FACTORS OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN TAMIL NADU

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Abstract:

That can't be achieved by intelligence, can be tactfully achieved by personality, and that is the influential power of personality. With or without our knowledge and will, we are influenced and fall a prey to the personality. Teachers who are with the kids from early childhood to adulthood influence a lot their students at every stage, and in this process the role of Big Five personality factors has an important role. This study investigated the Big Five personality of 1,405 prospective teachers chosen using simple random technique from the B.Ed. colleges. The statistical techniques arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and 't' test were used in the study. The findings of the study were as follows: The level of Big Five personality factors was high among the majority of the prospective teachers. The differential analysis revealed that there was no significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors agreeableness, conscientiousness and emotional stability. But there is significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion and openness. The male prospective teachers were found to be better than the female prospective teachers in their personality traits extroversion and openness. Further it revealed that there was no significant difference between the unmarried and the married prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness. But there was significant difference between the unmarried and married prospective teachers in their personality factor emotional stability. While comparing the mean scores of unmarried and married prospective teachers, the unmarried prospective teachers were better than the married prospective teachers in their personality trait emotional stability.

Key Words: Big Five Personality Factors, Extroversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability & Openness

Introduction:

Teaching is a gift. Being a teacher is noble. Teaching is professional and it is rewarding in one way and demanding in the other way. It is rewarding in multiple ways and the highest among them is the reputation that the teachers enjoy in the public and the sense of deep inner satisfaction that the teachers have at the bottom of their hearts. The dissemination of knowledge from the teacher gives life for the students. Teachers influence their students directly and indirectly; openly and in a hidden way; inside the class and outside the class. Apart from the knowledge, skills and attitude the teacher has, there are factors that mould and shape the students. One among them is the personality of the teachers. This article aims at exploring the Big Five personality traits among the prospective teachers.

Significance of the Study:

Personality is "the sum total of the behavioural and mental characteristics that are distinctive of an individual. Informally, it refers to the personal qualities that make a person socially popular" (Colman, A.M., 2009). The list of attributes or traits or factors that develops a person's personality is long. Psychologists have attempted a lot to list out elaborately and precisely enumerate those attributes. "Many contemporary personality psychologists believe that there are five basic dimensions of personality, often referred to as the "Big 5" personality traits. The five broad personality traits described by the theory are extraversion, agreeableness, openness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism" (Cherry, 2017, Para. 1). Teachers and prospective teachers interact with the students and their interactions influence their students a lot. Hence exploring these Big Five personality is significant as it affects the teaching-learning process.

Research Questions:

A research revolves around a problem of significance. The beginning of a research is identifying the problem for the study and so stating the problem of research brings clarity to the study. Kerlinger defines in the context of research "A problem is an interrogative sentence or statement that asks: What relation exists between two or more variables?" (as cited in Pandey & Pandey, 2015, p. 18).

- ✓ What is the level of Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers?
- ✓ Is there any significant difference in Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers with regard to their gender and marital status?

Operational Definition of the Key Terms:

- ✓ **Big Five Personality Factors:** It refers to the five important personality traits: 1. Extroversion, 2. Agreeableness. 3. Conscientiousness, 4. Emotional stability and 5. Openness (Cherry, 2017). In this study, the Big Five personality traits of prospective traits are measured by the scores obtained in the Big Five Inventory administered by the investigator.
- ✓ **Extroversion:** It is a trait characterized by sociability, talkativeness, assertiveness, and high amounts of emotional expressiveness. People who are high in this trait are outgoing and find it easy to make new friends. People who are low in it prefer solitude, find it difficult to start conversations and mingle with people.
- ✓ **Agreeableness:** It is a trait characterized by trust, altruism, kindness, affection, and other pro-social behaviors. People who are high in this trait tend to be more cooperative, enjoy helping and contributing to the happiness of other people. People who are low in it tend to have little interest in other people's problems, insult and belittle others, and be more competitive.
- ✓ **Conscientiousness:** It is a trait characterized by thoughtfulness, with good impulse control and goal-directed behaviours. People who are high in this trait tend to be organized, spend time in preparing, finish important tasks in time, and stick to their schedules. People who are low in it tend to dislike structure and schedules, procrastinate, and fail to complete the things they are supposed to do.
- ✓ **Emotional Stability:** It is a trait characterized by resilience, and balanced attitude. It is negatively termed as neuroticism. People who are high in this trait tend to deal well with stress, don't worry much, and very relaxed. People who are low in it tend to experience mood swings, anxiety, irritability, and sadness.
- ✓ **Openness:** It is a trait characterized by imagination, insight, and creativity. People who are high in this trait tend to have a broad range of interests, willing to take up new challenges. People who are low in openness are often more traditional, dislike change, resist new ideas and struggle with abstract thinking.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers with regard to their gender, and marital status.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers with respect to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers with respect to marital status.

Methodology:

The investigator used survey method to investigate the Big Five personality factors of Prospective Teachers. Survey research is the widely used method in social sciences. It "refers to the set of methods used to gather data in a systematic way from a range of individuals, organizations, or other units of interest (Julien, 2008..p. 846).

Population:

The population for the study includes all the prospective teachers who are doing B.Ed. degree course in the colleges of Education in Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Kanyakumari districts of Tamil Nadu.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample present study consists of 442 prospective teachers from Tirunelveli, 487 prospective teachers from Thoothukudi, and 476 prospective teachers from Kanyakumari districts. Simple random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample.

Tool Used:

Big Five Personality Inventory developed and validated by the investigator and the guide was used for collecting the data. John and Srivastava's Big Five Inventory served as the source for constructing the tool for the study.

Statistical Techniques Used:

The investigator used mean, standard deviation, and 't' test to analyse the collected data.

Analysis of Data:

Descriptive Analysis:

Objective 1: To find out the level of Big Five personality factors of prospective teachers

Table 1: Level of Big Five personality factors of Prospective Teachers

Personality Factors	Low		High	
	N	%	N	%
1. Extroversion	206	14.7	1199	85.3
2. Agreeableness	249	17.7	1156	82.3

3. Conscientiousness	213	15.2	1192	84.8
4. Emotional stability	223	15.9	1182	84.1
5. Openness	221	15.7	1184	84.3

It is inferred from the above table that 14.7% of prospective teachers have low and 85.3% of them have high level of extroversion. 17.7% of prospective teachers have low and 82.3% of them have high level of agreeableness. 15.2% of prospective teachers have low and 84.8% of them have high level of conscientiousness. 15.9% of prospective teachers have low and 84.1% of them have high level of emotional stability. 15.7% of prospective teachers have low and 84.3% of them have high level of openness.

Differential Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their Big Five personality factors (1) extroversion, (2) agreeableness, (3) conscientiousness, (4) emotional stability, and (5) openness.

Table 2: Difference between the Male and the Female Prospective Teachers in their Big Five Personality Factors

Personality Factors	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
1. Extroversion	Male	317	37.73	9.501	2.96	S
	Female	1088	35.92	9.793		
2. Agreeableness	Male	317	33.00	7.342	1.92	NS
	Female	1088	33.85	6.769		
3. Conscientiousness	Male	317	30.74	5.985	0.73	NS
	Female	1088	30.46	5.833		
4. Emotional Stability	Male	317	30.25	5.823	1.29	NS
	Female	1088	29.77	5.853		
5. Openness	Male	317	30.05	6.031	2..91	S
	Female	1088	28.35	5.797		

Note. The table value of 't' is 1.96; NS = not significant.

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value of personality factors, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability (1.92, 0.73, 1.29) are less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis with respect to agreeableness, conscientiousness and emotional stability is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors agreeableness, conscientiousness and emotional stability.

But the calculated 't' value of personality factors, extroversion and openness (2.96, 2.91) are greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis with respect to extroversion and openness are rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion and openness. While comparing the mean scores of male and female prospective teachers, the male (Mean = 37.73, 30.05) are better than the female (Men = 35.92, 28.35) prospective teachers in their personality traits extroversion and openness.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the unmarried and the married prospective teachers in their Big Five personality factors (1) extroversion, (2) agreeableness, (3) conscientiousness, (4) emotional stability, and (5) openness.

Table 3: Difference between the Unmarried and the Married Prospective Teachers in their Big Five Personality Factors

Personality Factors	Marital Status	N	Mean	S.D.	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
1. Extroversion	Unmarried	1194	32.22	5.528	1.22	NS
	Married	211	31.72	5.628		
2. Agreeableness	Unmarried	1194	33.78	6.759	1.59	NS
	Married	211	32.96	7.684		
3. Conscientiousness	Unmarried	1194	30.41	5.733	1.74	NS
	Married	211	31.17	6.549		
4. Emotional Stability	Unmarried	1194	37.57	9.562	2.33	S
	Married	211	35.90	9.676		
5. Openness	Unmarried	1194	28.57	5.878	1.24	NS
	Married	211	28.02	5.548		

Note: The table value of 't' is 1.96; NS = not significant.

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value of personality factors extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness (1.22, 1.59, 1.74, 1.24) are less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the result shows that there is no significant difference between the unmarried and the married prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness.

But the calculated 't' value of personality factor emotional stability (2.33) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis with respect to emotional stability is

rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between the unmarried and married prospective teachers in their personality factor emotional stability. While comparing the mean scores of unmarried and married prospective teachers, the unmarried (Mean = 37.57) prospective teachers were better than the married (Mean = 35.90) prospective teachers in their personality trait emotional stability.

Findings:

- ✓ The percentage analysis on the Big Five factors of personality revealed that the level of extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness for majority of the prospective teachers is high.
- ✓ The differential analysis revealed that there was no significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors agreeableness, conscientiousness and emotional stability. But there is significant difference between the male and the female prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion and openness. The male prospective teachers were found to be better than the female prospective teachers in their personality traits extroversion and openness.
- ✓ The differential analysis revealed that there was no significant difference between the unmarried and the married prospective teachers in their personality factors extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness. But there was significant difference between the unmarried and married prospective teachers in their personality factor emotional stability. While comparing the mean scores of unmarried and married prospective teachers, the unmarried (Mean = 37.57) prospective teachers were better than the married (Mean = 35.90) prospective teachers in their personality trait emotional stability.

Conclusion:

“The performance of the students is largely depends on the behavior of the teachers” (Kappagoda, 2013). A teacher’s behaviour to influence and cause behavioural change among the students is largely dependent on the personality that s/he has. The term personality is a global and inclusive term. To narrow down the complete personality of an individual into certain limited entities might be a half-ended task. Still a series of research efforts have proved the greater influence on one’s personality. Teachers being involved in human-to-human interaction in a formal instructional process, they need to develop their personality. The present study suggests that the prospective teachers have high level of personality in the Big Five factors which is an encouraging sign. It suggests that they are capable of influencing their students and they should be now further guided to develop these Big Five personality traits among their students. Female prospective teachers may be given trainings and seminar to develop extroversion and openness traits as they are found to be lower than their counter parts. The married prospective teachers may be given counselling to develop their emotional stability. Developing these Big Five traits may be contributing to be better in their teaching profession.

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